

1 ms23237@iisermohali.ac.in

2 **Scaling Properties of Avalanche Activity in the Two-Dimensional**
3 **Abelian Sandpile Model**

4 Anubhav Ganguly¹

5 ¹*Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Mohali, India*
6 *ICTS-TIFR, Bengaluru, India.*

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Abstract

We study the scaling properties of avalanche activity in the two-dimensional Abelian Sandpile Model by analyzing the total number of topplings at a site, summed over all possible grain addition sites in a fixed recurrent configuration. For each site, we define the avalanche activity ($A_C(R)$) as the sum of topplings at the site R due to grain addition at a site R' , summed over the entire lattice for a fixed configuration C . Using numerical simulations on square lattices of various sizes, we compute the probability distribution of this activity by averaging over C for a fixed Lattice size and find that it exhibits finite-size scaling of the form $P(A = a, L) = L^{-2}F(a/L^2)$. The scaling function $F(u)$ shows two regimes: for small u , it follows a power-law decay $F(u) \sim u^{-1/2}$, while for larger values it decays rapidly in an exponential form $F(u) \sim \exp(-au - bu^2)$ where a and b are constants.

8 I. INTRODUCTION

9 The Abelian Sandpile Model (ASM), introduced by Bak, Tang, and Wiesenfeld [1, 2], is
10 a paradigmatic example of self-organized criticality (SOC). In SOC systems, a slowly driven
11 dissipative system naturally evolves into a critical state without fine-tuning of parameters,
12 exhibiting scale invariance, power-law distributions, and long-range correlations [3, 4]. The
13 term “Abelian Sandpile Model” was introduced later, and the model has since been exten-
14 sively studied in both physics and mathematics [5–8].

15 Majumdar and Dhar [9] established the equivalence between the ASM and the $q \rightarrow 0$ limit
16 of the q -state Potts model, showing that the two-dimensional ASM can be described by a
17 conformal field theory with central charge $c = -2$. This mapping allows exact determination
18 of certain critical exponents, including the dynamic exponent $z = 5/4$ associated with the
19 growth of avalanche fronts under the burning algorithm [10].

20 Studies of the ASM traditionally focus on avalanche statistics. Let $N_C(R', R)$ denote
21 the number of topplings at site R' when a grain is added at site R , starting from a stable
22 configuration C . The total avalanche size is

$$s_C(R) = \sum_{R'} N_C(R', R).$$

23 Much effort has gone into characterizing the asymptotic form

$$\text{Prob}_\infty(s) \sim s^{-\tau},$$

24 defined as the probability of $s_C = s$ for lattice size tends to ∞ , with extensive numerical and
 25 analytical work devoted to estimating the avalanche exponent τ . While the exact value of
 26 τ remains elusive, it is well established that the mean avalanche size scales as $\langle s \rangle \sim L^2$ [11].

27 Analytical studies [12, 13] and numerical simulations [11, 14] have shown that the stochas-
 28 tic variation, called the Manna model, shares some universal features with the determin-
 29 istic ASM introduced by Bak, Tang, and Wiesenfeld. However, extended numerical anal-
 30 yses of critical exponents, multifractal analyses [15, 16], and studies of sandpiles as closed
 31 systems [18] show that deterministic and stochastic models belong to distinct universality
 32 classes.

33 Following the framework of Engsig and Sneppen [17], we focus on the complementary
 34 observable

$$A_C(R) = \sum_{R'} N_C(R, R'),$$

35 which measures the total activity at site R when grains are added randomly, keeping the
 36 background configuration C fixed. The total activity satisfies

$$\sum_R A_C(R) = \sum_R s_C(R),$$

37 so that $\langle A \rangle = \langle s \rangle$. The distribution of A has not been systematically analyzed previously in
 38 literature.

39 Let $P(A, L)$ denote the Probability Distribution Function of $A_C(R)$ over a randomly
 40 chosen C from the steady state. We investigate the distribution $\text{Prob}(A, L)$ of site activities
 41 in the two-dimensional ASM. Unlike avalanche sizes, $\text{Prob}(A, L)$ tends to zero for fixed A
 42 as $L \rightarrow \infty$, and follows a scaling form

$$P(A = a, L) = \frac{1}{L^2} F\left(\frac{a}{L^2}\right),$$

43 with distinct behavior for small a . Our numerical results show $F(u) \sim u^{-1/2}$ for small u and
 44 $F(u) \sim e^{-au-bu^2}$ for $u \gtrsim 0.1$, with $a \sim 10$ and $b \sim O(1)$.

45 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II, we define the ASM and the
 46 activity observable. Sec. III describes the numerical simulations and data analysis. Sec. IV
 47 presents results on activity scaling. Sec. V discusses implications and broader connections.

48 **II. MODEL AND DEFINITIONS**

49 We analyze the classical two-dimensional Bak–Tang–Wiesenfeld (BTW) Abelian sandpile
 50 model on a square lattice of size $L \times L$, as described in . Each site (x, y) has an integer-valued
 51 height $\Delta_{x,y} \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in the relaxed state, and $\Delta_{x,y} \geq 4$ indicates an unstable (excited)
 52 site.

53 A grain is added to a randomly selected site (x, y) , so that:

$$\Delta_{x,y} \rightarrow \Delta_{x,y} + 1.$$

54 If $\Delta_{x,y} \geq 4$, the site relaxes by distributing one grain to each of its four neighbors:

$$\Delta_{x,y} \rightarrow \Delta_{x,y} - 4, \quad \Delta_{x\pm 1,y} \rightarrow \Delta_{x\pm 1,y} + 1, \quad \Delta_{x,y\pm 1} \rightarrow \Delta_{x,y\pm 1} + 1.$$

55 This toppling may trigger further relaxations. The process continues until all $\Delta_{x,y} < 4$
 56 Open boundary conditions are used: when a boundary site topples, excess grains exit the
 57 system. Only once the lattice is stable again (i.e., all $\Delta_{x,y} < 4$), a new grain is added.

58 Given a stable configuration C of the lattice, and a site position R , we define the *ex-*
 59 *citability function* as

$$s_C(R) = \text{Size of the avalanche triggered by adding a grain at } R.$$

60 If the addition at R causes no topplings, then $s_C(R) = 0$. Sites with $s_C(R) > 0$ are called
 61 *excitable*, while those that trigger large avalanches—for example, $s_C(R) > 0.1L^2$ —are called
 62 *highly excitable*.

63 To compute $s_C(R)$, a grain is added at R , the avalanche is simulated, and the system is
 64 then reset to the original configuration C . This procedure is repeated for all sites.

65 The *activity function* quantifies the total number of topplings that a site R undergoes
 66 when avalanches are initiated at all possible sites of the lattice on the same configuration C :

$$A_C(R) = \sum_{R'} N_C(R, R'),$$

67 where $N_C(R, R')$ is the number of topplings at site R due to an avalanche triggered by adding
 68 a grain at site R' in configuration C .

69 This function highlights which regions of the lattice are most frequently involved in
 70 avalanche propagation.

FIG. 1. The heatmap of function s for a configuration of lattice size 200

FIG. 2. The heatmap of function A for the same configuration, normalised by L^2

71 Previous analyses have found that the expectation of s scales as approximately $0.08 L^2$
 72 [11]. We confirm this behavior in our simulations by computing the lattice average of A ,
 73 and we find

$$\langle A \rangle = \langle s \rangle \approx 0.085 L^2.$$

FIG. 3. Plot of the expectation values $\langle A \rangle$ and $\langle s \rangle$ as a function of L , verifying that $\langle A \rangle = \langle s \rangle$.

74 III. NUMERICAL PROCEDURE AND DETAILS OF SIMULATIONS

75 Simulations were performed on lattice sizes ranging from $L = 20$ to 160 on open boundary
 76 conditions. For each size, the system was allowed to reach a critical state and then averaged
 77 over 10,000 configurations to compute $A(R)$, and subsequently the empirical probability
 78 distribution $P(A = a, L)$. To determine $A(R)$, we fix the configuration C , and add a

79 particle at R' , counting the number of topplings at R , then reset to configuration C , add at
 80 a different site, and sum the activity at R over all points of addition.

81 We analyze the probability distribution $P(A = a, L)$, where $A(R)$ denotes the number of
 82 topplings at site $R=(i, j)$, accumulated over many randomly initiated avalanches. Data were
 83 collected for system sizes ranging from $L = 20$ to $L = 160$, averaging over 10^4 configurations
 84 per size.

85 We plot the probability distribution $P(A = a, L)$ for small avalanche activity a , and we
 86 find that for fixed values of $a \ll L^2$, the probability scales inversely with the linear system
 87 size:

$$P(A = a, L) \sim \frac{g(a)}{L}.$$

FIG. 4. Log-log plot of $g(a) = LP(A = a, L)$ versus a for small a . The slope of the straight line indicates $g(a) \sim a^x$ with $x = -0.385 \pm 0.03$. $R^2 = 0.98$ for fit. The data can also be fitted fairly well with the form $g(x) \approx c_1 x^{-1/2} + c_2$ where x is a/L^2 and c_1, c_2 are constants numerically determined.

88 This trend is illustrated in Fig. 5, where we plot $\log P(A = a)$ against $\log L$ for small
 89 fixed values of a . The slope of approximately -1 ± 0.015 confirms the $1/L$ dependence.

90 Unified Scaling Form Across Avalanche Sizes

91 The full distribution is well described by a single finite-size scaling form:

$$P(A = a, L) \sim \frac{1}{L^2} F\left(\frac{a}{L^2}\right), \quad F(u) = (c_1 u^{-0.5} + c_2) e^{-c_3 u - c_4 u^2},$$

FIG. 5. Log-log plot of $P(A = a)$ vs. L for small fixed values of a . The observed slope of -1 indicates $P(A = a) \sim 1/L$. Dashed line given as a reference for slope -1

FIG. 6. Scaling collapse of $P(A, L)$ for $L=60,160$ log-binned with the fitted form with $c_1 = 6.81$, $c_2 = 0.5$, $c_3 = 10.0$.

FIG. 7. Semilog plot of $P(A, L)$ vs. A ; linear for $A > 0.1L^2$, indicating exponential regime, with $c_3 = 10.0 \pm 0.12$

92 where c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 are constants determined from fits to simulation data.

93 For small avalanches ($a \ll L^2$), the argument $u = a/L^2 \ll 1$, and the scaling function is
 94 dominated by the term $c_1 u^{-0.5} + c_2$. Substituting $u = a/L^2$ gives

$$F(u) \sim c_1 u^{-0.5} + c_2 = c_1 \frac{L}{a^{0.5}} + c_2.$$

95 Thus, the probability becomes

$$P(A = a, L) \sim \frac{1}{L^2} \cdot F(u) \sim \frac{1}{L} \cdot \frac{c_1}{a^{0.5}} + \frac{c_2}{L^2},$$

96 recovering the observed $1/L$ scaling for small avalanche sizes. The observed decrease of

97 $\text{Prob}(A)$ in the log-log plot gives a slope less steep than $-\frac{1}{2}$. This may be explained by the
 98 inclusion of the constant c_2 , with the value of c_2 adjusted to give an observed slope of
 99 ~ -0.385 in the small a regime.

100 For large avalanches ($A \sim \mathcal{O}(L^2)$), the exponential term $e^{-c_3 u - c_4 u^2}$ dominates, ensuring
 101 a rapid decay of $P(A, L)$

102 This unified scaling form therefore captures both the small- A $1/L$ trend and the large- A
 103 bulk suppression within a single analytic expression.

104 The scaling analysis of the activity distribution $P(A, L)$ reveals a crossover in its func-
 105 tional form. As shown in Fig. 5, the distribution follows a power-law-like scaling for small
 106 A but undergoes a crossover to an exponential decay for larger avalanche activities. This
 107 crossover occurs at a specific scale $A^* \sim 0.1L^2$. In other words, there exists a crossover scale
 108 A^* such that for $A \ll A^*$ the distribution exhibits power-law behavior, while for $A \gg A^*$ it
 109 is dominated by exponential decay. A key finding of this work is that for a fixed A , $\text{Prob}(A)$
 110 goes to 0 as L tends to ∞

111 FIG. 8. Plot of the $\langle A \rangle / L^3$ and as a function of ϵ showing linear trend, indicating $\langle A \rangle \sim \epsilon L^3$ as
 112 the leading order term.

113 Consider a rare configuration C_ϵ in an $L \times L$ Abelian Sandpile Model (ASM), where the
 114 total mass of the configuration exceeds from C by an amount ϵL^2 without changing the
 115 number of active height 3 sites.

116 We can see via simulations by generating such configurations C_ϵ that

$$\langle A \rangle_{C_\epsilon} \sim \epsilon L^3.$$

117 We can see that the fractional number of states $C_\epsilon \sim \exp(-\epsilon^2 L^2)$

118 This gives us $F(x \sim \epsilon L) \gtrsim \exp(-x^2)$, for large $x \sim \epsilon L$, giving rise to the $\exp(-bu^2)$ term
119 in the scaling function

120 IV. SCALING THEORY

121 We start by assuming a general scaling form for the avalanche size distribution $P(A, L)$:

$$P(A = a; L) \sim L^{-\alpha} F\left(\frac{a}{L^\beta}\right),$$

122 where α and β are scaling exponents to be determined, and $F(u)$ is a scaling function of
123 $u = a/L^\beta$.

124 *a. Normalization Condition:* The total probability must satisfy

$$\sum_a P(A = a; L) = 1.$$

125 Substituting the scaling form and approximating the sum by an integral for large L :

$$\sum_a P(A = a; L) \sim \int_0^\infty L^{-\alpha} F\left(\frac{a}{L^\beta}\right) da.$$

126 Changing variables $u = a/L^\beta \implies da = L^\beta du$:

$$\sum_a P(A = a; L) \sim \int_0^\infty L^{-\alpha} F(u) L^\beta du = L^{\beta-\alpha} \int_0^\infty F(u) du.$$

127 For normalization to hold independently of L , we must have

$$\alpha = \beta.$$

128 *b. Expectation Value:* The expected avalanche size scales as

$$\langle A \rangle = \sum_a a P(A = a; L) \sim \int_0^\infty a L^{-\alpha} F\left(\frac{a}{L^\beta}\right) da.$$

129 Changing variables $u = a/L^\beta \implies da = L^\beta du$:

$$\langle A \rangle \sim \int_0^\infty (L^\beta u) L^{-\alpha} F(u) L^\beta du = L^{2\beta-\alpha} \int_0^\infty u F(u) du.$$

130 Since theory and simulations indicate $\langle A \rangle \sim L^2$, we require

$$2\beta - \alpha = 2 \implies \beta = 2, \alpha = 2.$$

131 *c. Small- and Large- u Behavior:* The scaling function $F(u)$ controls the shape of the
 132 distribution:

- 133 • For small $u \lesssim 0.1$, assuming $F(u) \sim u^{-1/2}$, we obtain $P(A) \sim 1/L$.
- 134 • For large values $u \gtrsim 0.1$, numerics suggest that $F(u) \sim \exp(-c_3u - c_4u^2)$, with $c_3 \sim 10$
 135 and $c_4 = O(1)$. As ϵ approaches the critical value such that all sites have height 3, the
 136 fraction of such configurations is of order $\exp(-c_4u^2)$, indicating that $c_4 = O(1)$.

137 V. DISCUSSION

138 Our results indicate that the avalanche activity distribution $P(A = a)$ is best described
 139 by a single scaling form of the type

$$P(A = a; L) \sim \frac{1}{L^2} F\left(\frac{a}{L^2}\right),$$

140 where the scaling function $F(u)$ captures both the small- and large-avalanche behavior. A
 141 suitable form that accounts for the observed piecewise behavior is

$$F(u) \approx (c_1 u^{-0.5} + c_2) e^{-c_3 u - c_4 u^2}.$$

142 In this formulation, the first term dominates for small u ($a \ll L^2$), reproducing the effective
 143 $1/L$ scaling observed in the boundary-driven small-avalanche regime, while the exponential
 144 term governs the large- u ($a \sim L^2$) decay, corresponding to the bulk-dominated avalanches.

145 For small avalanches, the data collapse reveals that

$$L^2 P(A; L) \sim c_1 \left(\frac{a}{L^2}\right)^{-0.5} + c_2 \quad \text{OR} \quad P(A; L) \sim \frac{1}{L} a^{-0.385}.$$

146 consistent with the observed slope in the pre-cutoff region. This demonstrates that bound-
 147 ary effects generate a scale-free contribution, yet the system-wide average is dominated by
 148 larger avalanches.

149 Studying the site activity $A(R)$, rather than the conventional avalanche size $s(R)$, is
 150 crucial because it shifts the focus from global avalanche statistics to local participation
 151 patterns. While $s(R)$ tells us how large an avalanche starts at a site, $A(R)$ measures how
 152 often a site participates in avalanches started anywhere in the system—essentially mapping
 153 the *hotspots* of avalanche propagation. This provides fundamentally different information

FIG. 9. Scaling collapse of $P(A, L)$ for multiple system sizes using log binned data

154 about the internal dynamics of self-organized criticality, characterizing which regions serve as
 155 frequent conduits for activity spread. Understanding this local activity landscape is essential
 156 for connecting sandpile models to real-world systems where only partial observations are
 157 possible—such as neural recording electrodes or local strain sensors—and may ultimately
 158 help decode how global criticality emerges from local interacting thresholds.

159 Overall, the scaling form provides a unified description that satisfies both normalization
 160 and the expected $\langle A \rangle \sim L^2$, while accurately capturing the observed distribution across all
 161 avalanche sizes.

162 We note some significant deviations from the asymptotic behavior. In particular, the proba-
 163 bility of exactly $A = 2$ topplings shows a pronounced dip, reflecting combinatorial constraints
 164 in the allowed toppling sequences.

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171 [1] P. Bak, C. Tang, and K. Wiesenfeld, Phys. Rev. Lett. **59**, 381 (1987).

- 172 [2] P. Bak, C. Tang, and K. Wiesenfeld, *Phys. Rev. A* **38**, 364 (1988).
- 173 [3] D. Dhar, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **64**, 1613 (1990).
- 174 [4] D. Dhar, *Physica A* **263**, 4 (1999).
- 175 [5] P. Bak, *How Nature Works: The Science of Self-Organized Criticality*, Springer, 1996.
- 176 [6] F. Redig, *Mathematical aspects of the Abelian sandpile model*, in *Mathematics of Complexity*
177 *and Dynamical Systems*, Springer, 2011.
- 178 [7] E. Goles and A. Járai, *Sandpile Models: An Overview*, in *Discrete Dynamical Systems*,
179 Springer, 2002.
- 180 [8] G. Pruessner, *Self-Organised Criticality: Theory, Models and Characterisation*, Cambridge
181 University Press, 2012.
- 182 [9] S. N. Majumdar and D. Dhar, *Physica A* **185**, 129 (1992).
- 183 [10] D. Dhar, P. Ruelle, S. Sen, and D.-N. Verma, *J. Phys. A* **28**, 805 (1995).
- 184 [11] Y. Shilo and O. Biham, "Sandpile models and random walkers on finite lattices," *Phys. Rev.*
185 *E* **67**, 066102 (2003).
- 186 [12] S. S. Manna, *J. Phys. A* **24**, L363 (1991).
- 187 [13] V. B. Priezzhev and K. Sneppen, *Phys. Rev. E* **58**, 6959 (1998).
- 188 [14] A. Ben-Hur and O. Biham, *Phys. Rev. E* **53**, R1317 (1996).
- 189 [15] S. Ostojic, *Physica A* **318**, 187 (2003).
- 190 [16] L. Levine, W. Pegden, and C. K. Smart, *Geom. Funct. Anal.* **26**, 306 (2016).
- 191 [17] M. Engsig and K. Sneppen, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **134**, 187201 (2025).
- 192 [18] V. Frette, K. Christensen, A. Mølhave-Sørensen, J. Feder, T. Jossang, and P. Meakin, *Nature*
193 **379**, 49 (1996).